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Abstract

This document provides a summary of the Technology Task (Task 1) and Platform Task (Task 2) work within the Network Development Work Package (WP6) of the GN5-2 project. It summarises progress in the assessment of emerging network technologies relevant to the research and education community, including quantum technologies, network programmability, fibre sensing, and long-haul White Rabbit time distribution. It also describes the continued development of platforms that support experimentation, service management, automation, and orchestration. These include GP4L, network service orchestration workflows and source-of-truth solutions, and the nmaas platform, together with incubator activities focused on AI-supported log analysis and retrieval-augmented interaction with orchestration systems. The work focuses on combining technology exploration with practical platform development with the aim to provide reusable foundations, operational best practices, and community-facing support for innovation in NREN infrastructures and services.

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Executive Summary

This document summarises the work conducted as part of the Technology Task (Task 1) and Platform Task (Task 2) within the Network Development Work Package (WP6) of the GN5-2 project focusing on the development, assessment, and practical application of network technologies and platforms relevant to the research and education community.

The work reported in this document shows steady progress across several areas that are important for the future evolution of research and education networking, combining early-stage investigation of emerging technologies with the development of practical environments, tools, and workflows that can support experimentation, service delivery, and operational innovation. In addition to advancing knowledge in selected technical domains, both tasks have produced concrete assets, deployment experience, and community-facing outputs that help reduce the distance between exploration and practical uptake.

An important highlight is the continued maturation of several technology areas with clear relevance for future NREN services and infrastructures.

- Work on quantum technologies has moved beyond general awareness raising and has addressed concrete questions related to key management, interoperability, operational aspects, and quantum-safe networking, while also expanding the associated training offer for the community.
- In network programmability, the work has continued to build on established efforts around RARE while also responding to changing hardware realities and extending experimentation towards new use cases, including those linked to quantum communication.
- Fibre sensing has progressed from exploratory interest towards a more structured understanding of user requirements, deployment challenges, and possible service models, supported by direct engagement with NRENs.
- The incubator on long-haul White Rabbit time distribution has provided particularly valuable practical evidence by showing that precise terrestrial time services can be delivered over existing long-haul optical infrastructure, offering a promising and more cost-effective option for future deployment.
- Within Platform development, GP4L enabled users to reserve the whole or selected parts of the infrastructure in order to test networking functionalities, validate software solutions, explore custom implementations of routing operating systems and protocols, and develop and execute their own P4 code on programmable hardware. In addition, network service orchestration demonstrated the operational use of Maat and AI-Assisted orchestration.

Taken together, these activities show a clear emphasis on technologies that are not only innovative, but also potentially actionable in realistic NREN contexts.

In parallel, significant progress has also been made in the platform and automation work. The reported activities show that WP6 Task 2 is building not only experimental capability, but also reusable operational foundations. GP4L continues to serve as an important infrastructure for programmable networking experimentation. The orchestration activities have advanced reusable automated workflows, strengthened the role of source-of-truth-driven service management through Maat, and explored how artificial intelligence (AI) can support both

workflow development and controlled orchestration scenarios. At the same time, the nmaas platform has continued to evolve as a multi-tenant environment that supports production and pilot use cases for network management, training, analytics and monitoring. The incubator activities on automated log analysis and retrieval-augmented interaction with orchestration systems further show that AI-related work is being approached in a practical way, with attention to explainability, structured integration, and operational usefulness rather than technology experimentation alone. Overall, the document indicates that the platform work is becoming increasingly relevant as a basis for repeatable, modular, and community-reusable solutions.

In summary, activities in the area of quantum, fibre sensing, network programmability are still at a very early maturity stage and these results could be considered for evaluation of the future testing and deployment of these technologies in R&E networks, rather than a production-ready solutions. While the time distribution using White Rabbit incubator provided some very tangible and practical results, and similar solutions are in production in some NRENS, there are still some prerequisites need to be fulfilled for this to become a widely accepted and deployed solution. The prerequisites include, but are not limited to, overall plans for time and frequency distribution in NRENS using optical networks, roadmap for such a network development and services offering, budgeting, human resources etc. The results are however very indicative and are used for planning of the next steps in OTFN.

In addition, the work on AI-supported network operations should also be seen as guidelines and applied practices rather than an off-the-shelf ready-to-deploy solution. On the other hand, activities that provide ready-to-use, production or production-level solutions are nmaas - production service since 2019, used by many organisations in Europe and worldwide in two production use cases of vNOC and vLab, as well as in two developing use cases of Metrics and Monitoring, Maat - service and resources inventory tool, already in production in PCSS and RENATER, and GP4L.

A consistent element throughout the reported activities is the effort to produce outcomes that are useful beyond the immediate scope of the individual developments. This includes white papers, workshops, infoshares, conference presentations, public articles, training materials, documentation, and reusable software and workflow components.

Ultimately, the work described in this document shows continued progress in areas that are important for the future evolution of NREN infrastructures and services, while also providing platforms, tools, experience and reference implementations that can support further experimentation, adoption and collaboration across the community.

1 Introduction

The development of network infrastructures, services, and operational capabilities requires both the assessment of emerging technologies and the availability of suitable platforms for experimentation, validation, and service evolution. New technological directions may open opportunities for the research and education (R&E) community, but their practical relevance depends on clearly identified use cases, careful evaluation, and the ability to test them in realistic environments. At the same time, platforms, tools, and automation solutions are essential for translating promising concepts into operational practice and for supporting collaboration, reuse, and innovation across National Research and Education Networks (NRENs).

Within the GN5-2 project, the Network Development Work Package (WP6), two tasks: Technology (Task 1) and Platforms (Task 2), contributes to this area by focusing on network technologies and platforms relevant to the research and education community. The work addresses both the investigation of selected emerging technology areas and the development and maintenance of platforms that support experimentation, service management, automation, orchestration, and operational innovation. These activities are carried out taking into account the technical feasibility, operational relevance, community needs, and opportunities for wider reuse across the GÉANT community.

Training and dissemination are also critical components in this context: educational opportunities are vital for the adoption and understanding of emerging technologies within a community. In a broad community like GÉANT, training initiatives and knowledge exchange contribute to building a shared understanding of fundamental baselines, definitions, and terminology. Establishing common knowledge and reference frameworks further aids in creating effective policies for new services, facilitates rapid service adoption, and enhances as well as simplifies opportunities for collaborative efforts across multiple domains or among different NRENs.

This document presents the work carried out from the start of the project in January 2025 to the end of March 2026. In addition to technical development, the document also reflects the broader effort to support community uptake through validation activities, documentation, training, dissemination, and the sharing of practical experience.

Section 2 Network Technologies highlights the progress in emerging technology areas, such as: quantum technologies, network programmability and fibre sensing, including the incubator focused on Long-Haul White Rabbit Time Distribution.

Section 3, Platforms, details the Global Platform for Labs (GP4L), Network Service Orchestration, and nmaas (previously Network Management as a Service, NMaaS), along with work completed in two incubators covering Automated Log Analysis Using Large Language Models, as well as the Workflow Orchestrator RAG agent and LLM integration. Section 4 provides overall conclusions and key observations.

Overall conclusions and observations can be found in Section 4.

2 Network Technologies

The Technology task explores emerging infrastructure technologies, their relevance and applicability for the NREN use cases and readiness and maturity for future operational services. This task includes four areas of work: quantum technologies, network programmability and RARE (Router for Academia, Research and Education), fibre sensing and also work completed as part of a 9-month incubator exploring Long-haul White Rabbit Time Distribution in the context of the GÉANT Core Time and Frequency Network C-TFN. All focus areas are being investigated from the perspective of the services they can offer, how cross-border challenges could be tackled, and how the development can be most beneficial in the support of the NREN community. The work of Task 1 was introduced as part of a GN5-2 Milestone event “Network Technologies Workshop” [1]. The following sections provide more details on the work of each subtask, and also the incubator.

2.1 Quantum Technology

In GN5-2 the subtask “Quantum Technology” in Work Package 6 Task 1 continued to explore network requirements for the implementation of quantum technologies-related services for the GÉANT community. As part of this work, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) has been in focus as one of the quantum technologies that is commercially available. National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) have started experimenting with QKD in national and international projects. One main component of QKD is its Key Management System (KMS) which is responsible for handling the lifecycle and storage of keys generated by QKD devices. To investigate key management as a potential service within the GÉANT community a KMS pathfinder was deployed between five locations within four countries (Germany, Poland, Spain and Greece). A central KMS to serve these five locations was put in place by GÉANT-IT in a sixth location (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: KMS Pathfinder deployment

The KMS pathfinder in its current installation connects these locations via IPsec tunnels (as for this KMS study no actual Quantum-links need to be in place). Rather, the focus of the investigation lies on interoperability aspects, the creation, management and use of cryptographic keys, as well as potential requirements and possibilities for smooth and secure cross-domain quantum communication. Other aspects of interest are the exploration of certificate and authentication procedures as well as monitoring issues. As part of this work several open source KMS software packages were investigated for potential integration in the pathfinder; the software packages of the NREN SURF and also a software package developed by the University of the Basque Country (EHU) are employed in first tests within one domain. The simulation software QKDNetSim2.0 was also studied for potential use in connection with the KMS pathfinder.

To accompany this work on Key Management Systems, an infoshare “Quantum KMS Architectures and Services” [2] was organised. A related infoshare “Community-Built Quantum Communication Tools” [3] introduced the KMS software packages of SURF and EHU and provided more details on their current capabilities. In a third infoshare “Operational Aspects of Quantum Communication Networks” [4] multi-technology QKD networks operational aspects came into focus with issues such as how performance and stability of QKD links can be checked, monitored and verified, for example.

Another major focus in this subtask was an investigation on how to ensure that networks are quantum-safe. Quantum-safe networking refers to the adoption of cryptographic methods that are resistant to attacks by quantum computers. It involves the transition from classical cryptographic methods, which are vulnerable to quantum algorithms, to post-quantum cryptography (PQC) and quantum key distribution (QKD) systems that can withstand quantum threats. A white paper, “Towards Quantum-Safe Networking” [5], was published as a step-by-step approach towards quantum-safe networks where PQC and QKD technology is applied and integrated over time to harden networks and ensure quantum-safe security. To promote this work, a CONNECT article was also published [6].

As a commitment to quantum training and in cooperation with Work Package 6 Task 4 as well as the GÉANT GLAD team, the Network eAcademy track on Quantum Technology was extended with the publication of three learning units which also included a hands-on video. In a newly formed collaboration with the NREN GRNET and their HellasQCI training platform additional learning units were made available and led to the design of a new metro map (Figure 2.2)

Figure 2.2: New and extended QT metro map.

This work was highlighted in a presentation at the Fourth Open Monthly GNA-G Network eAcademy Working Group Meeting [7] as well as in two CONNECT articles featuring the Moodle courses on QKD as well as the new how-to video [8] [9].

To keep in touch with current issues that members of the community are facing, periodic Open Quantum Group Meetings have been part of GN5-1, where NRENs have had the opportunity to share news about their activities and could present topics in focus or possibilities for collaboration. To emphasise this effort, two Open Quantum Group Meetings were hosted, which also included an official introduction and handover into the new GÉANT SIG-Quantum [10] which is now providing a forum for the community working around quantum technologies, including quantum networking, computing, sensing, cryptography and communication across Research and Education Networks. The work in Task 1 related to Quantum Technologies was presented at the first SIG-Quantum meeting [11].

2.2 Network Programmability

Task 1 of Work Package 6 investigates the ability, advantages and use cases of open and programmable network elements in the R&E environment through continued development and support of the Router for Academia, Research and Education (RARE), which has gained significant interest from the community, worldwide. As part of this work, a comprehensive overview of the current state of network programmability and programmable networks was provided in a white paper “Programmable Networks: Current State and Trends” [12]. The document explores the historical evolution of programmable networks, their technological background, current implementations and possible future directions and opportunities for research and experimentation, particularly within GN5-2. The investigation lists some ongoing work being carried out in research and education institutions and NRENs. Examples include the use of white boxes and P4-programmable hardware. Special emphasis was put on the Router for Academia, Research, and Education (RARE) open-source operating system and the Global Platform for Labs (GP4L) – both developed over a few iterations of the GÉANT project. This white paper also underscores the importance of continued research and experimentation in network programmability to adapt to evolving technological trends.

Hardware availability options remained as a major topic in this subtask, with Intel’s announcement to no longer develop TOFINO switches based on Barefoot Networks chipset (Intel-TOFINO). The team looked into Tofino 1 and Tofino 2 availability options, but also explored new options potentially becoming available with Tahoe-3828 and Tahoe-3832 switches from Xsight Labs [13] and access to associated simulation software. In order to investigate trends and related work, the team also took part in various meetings of the Software for Open Networking in the Cloud (SONiC) Working Group [14] and presented RARE at FOSDEM 2025 in Brussels, Belgium, which is a conference for software development and users.

The RARE DDoS use case with the use of NeMo - DDoS software from WP8 was extended with a NeMo integration into freeRtr, and an investigation of NeMo mitigation components. A decision was made to move GÉANT repositories to the platform Codeberg [15] to facilitate worldwide access to software. This entailed additional testing of newer versions of NeMo. The RARE NeMo work is also detailed in a learning unit.

A new use case was started in the group and as a cross-subtask with subtask “Quantum Technologies”: The main focus of this new use case is the adaptation of network programmability in the context of QKD relays and scalability of quantum communications. The work investigates how classical Software Defined Networking (SDN) concepts can be applied to end-to-end security and control and path establishment also in the context of constraints such as heterogeneous networks that rely on both QKD-enabled nodes as well as on PQC-enabled classical nodes. A simulation platform was established, and the work is now being extended with an implementation on two switches that are part of Global P4 Lab (GP4L). The work was presented in the infoshare “Community-Built Quantum Communication Tools” [16].

2.3 Fibre Sensing

Fibre Sensing is a technology where existing optical fibres are used as a sensing instrument to gather information about network infrastructures and surroundings. The collected data can be extremely useful for management and preventive maintenance in the National Research and Education Network (NREN) context, but also to researchers in the fields of seismology, oceanography or marine zoology. After a successful incubator in the previous project, the fibre sensing work is now being continued as part of Work Package 6 Task 1 within GN5-2.

The work in the new project phase started with a focus on one of the major topics that need to be addressed as part of fibre sensing: The collection of data and how to manage access policies and security. In order to raise awareness in this field, the fibre sensing subtask organised the “Fibre Sensing & Data Acquisition Workshop”. In addition, a collaboration was started with GÉANT’s IPR coordinator to address the issues of data access and property rights.

In order to reach user communities, a white paper was published that focuses on “Technologies, Users and Use Cases for NRENs” [17]. This document provides a brief overview of fibre-sensing technologies and examines how fibre sensing offers NRENs the opportunity to enhance the monitoring and protection of their networks while simultaneously generating valuable data for scientific research and civil protection.

The white paper publication was followed up with a community survey sent to NRENs to get a clearer understanding of how NRENs are currently using or planning to use Fibre Sensing, what common challenges and opportunities they may face, and how GÉANT can support the community in accelerating the adoption and effective use of Fibre Sensing technologies. NRENs were invited via mailing list to complete the survey and 27 NRENs responded. In addition to the survey, there was also a series of interviews that were conducted with NRENs who had expressed strong interest in infrastructure monitoring as a potential Fibre Sensing use case as part of their survey response. The survey results suggest that interest in Fibre Sensing is present across many NRENs in Europe, but that there are structural and organisational constraints such as lack of ownership or direct control over fibre and DWDM infrastructure, equipment and operational costs as well as limited staff capacity. The survey also made clear that there are different levels of maturity among NRENs with some NRENs showing initial interest and investigating how Fibre Sensing could become useful for them, while others are already deploying it based on very clear use cases and results in mind. The results of the survey are currently being prepared to be published as a white paper and as part of an infoshare event.

To analyse the complete framework of a fibre sensing deployment, an analysis to map TM Forum’s Open Digital Architecture (ODA) [18] to GÉANT’s pilot deployment of fibre sensing was initiated. This effort will provide a more general blueprint for NRENs to see how their deployments can match common framework guidelines and enable collaboration through common APIs and how both single and multi-domain/federated aspects can be addressed.

GÉANT’s pilot deployment includes the recent installation of a DAS unit, which is collecting data that can now serve as input for more investigations. Tests in the laboratory included strain and temperature tests on fibre optic cables.

As a way to create interest and awareness for Fibre Sensing, a fun promotional video was completed right before Christmas on How fibre optics can track Santa’s travels [19]. An article in CONNECT magazine was also published called “Tapping into the ground: terrestrial applications of Distributed Fibre Sensing” [20]. The preparation of Fibre Sensing training was started, which will be a new track as part of the Network eAcademy with its own metro map (see Figure 2.3). The learning units will offer technological information, information on data management and will also include valuable use cases. A collaboration was started with the SUBMERSE project to offer additional links to their training platform as well.

Figure 2.3: First draft of the planned Fibre Sensing training track

For greater public awareness, several infoshares were conducted: A Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology infoshare with vendors called “Backscattering based sensing technologies, Equipment and Use Cases” [21] was organised; a second infoshare “State of Polarisation-Based Sensing on Optical Fibre” [22] was highlighted.

2.4 Incubator: Long-Haul White Rabbit Time Distribution

The incubator process within Work Package 6 provides a mechanism to include new areas of work throughout the duration of the project in an agile way. This is to ensure that early-stage technologies, community topics in focus or areas of concern can be investigated within a flexible timeline following a structured programme. As part of Task 1, incubator project “Long-haul White Rabbit Time Distribution” started with a dedicated timeline of 9 months. As there is currently significant investment by Horizon Europe to allow GÉANT to build a C-TFN network for time and frequency distribution services, the purpose of this incubator investigation was to determine if the time service could be carried on legacy long-haul DWDM systems with a lower cost than a dedicated fibre solution. While dedicated fibre is needed for frequency, time service has a lower stability requirement, but must be absolute (rather than relative) time, i.e. must include UTC timestamps. Five NRENs were involved in this incubator: CESNET, GÉANT, SUNET, FUNET, GARR.

Time and Frequency services have become essential for many applications with use cases ranging from financial transactions to energy Smart Grids, mobile networks, quantum metrology & National Metrological Institutes (NMIs) to terrestrial time service redundancy to GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite Systems).

For the past couple of years jamming and spoofing of GNSS has become more and more of a challenge for Europe and has increased pressure to complement the European Galileo satellite network with terrestrial solutions such as a fibre-based time distribution with White Rabbit (WR) technology developed by CERN [23]. Therefore, the incubator was conducted for European NRENs to help them decide on the best technical solution for deploying WR in their network.

White Rabbit (WR) technology enables sub-nanosecond time synchronisation and frequency precision in the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-12}$ over distributed networks using standard fibre optic links. It is based on but extends IEEE 1588 Precision Time Protocol (PTP) and Synchronous Ethernet (SyncE) and is now included as IEEE 1588 High Accuracy (HA) profile in the IEEE-2019 standard with additional enhancements such as precise hardware timestamps, compensation of delay asymmetry and phase measurement techniques.

There are different technical solutions for WR: The technology can be implemented on dedicated or shared fibres, with uni-directional or bidirectional transmission. The route length is also important: For routes with links longer than 80-100km regeneration of the signal must be applied which adds challenges in terms of latency, jitter and temperature stability.

The incubator project [24] investigated three different regeneration techniques: 1) using WR switches for regeneration, 2) optical-electrical-optical (OEO) regeneration and 3) using optical bidirectional amplifiers (EDFA). The incubator also explained several approaches to calibration, ranging from per-component calibration to whole setup calibration and loop topology calibration.

Both laboratory tests and field tests were conducted: in the lab, the three regeneration techniques were tested over 400km with regeneration at every 100km. The field test was a real-world implementation of WR on a long DWDM line system on the GÉANT route from Prague – Vienna, passing through node points Kouřim, Šachotin and Ivančice with DWDM amplifiers. The field test route carried optical signals on a single fibre bidirectionally using BiDi EDFA. For the integration of WR and Optical Supervisory Channel (OSC) signals, conventional DWDM L-Band and CWDM filters were in place. The field test took place with full live Internet traffic on coherent transmission in the C-Band ($2 \times 400\text{Gbit/s}$). The tests were conducted with two loops: The first loop ran over a WR route of 322km to Sachotin and the second loop included all four node points with a total WR time service link of 498km.

The field tests showed that the installation of White Rabbit technology did not affect the operating GÉANT data channels and corroborated the laboratory test. During a measurement period that lasted several weeks, it was demonstrated that a WR time transfer stability of ± 100 ps over the test route of 498km (118 dB total attenuation) utilising five bidirectional optical amplifiers could be achieved (even significantly exceeding the standard 1 ns requirement).

This demonstration of infrastructure coexistence is a very important result as it is a more cost-effective solution than running a redundant infrastructure of dark fibre for T&F services. In addition, a unified infrastructure allows leveraging of existing operational frameworks (for monitoring, troubleshooting or security) and provides scalability to reach end-users.

The incubator offered best practices and recommendations to NRENs on how to best implement such services. It also includes a cost calculator for NRENs to make informed deployment decisions. At the time of writing this document was in its final review stages before publication.

3 Platforms

The WP6 Task 2 team focuses on the development, maintenance, and practical use of platforms and solutions that support experimentation, service management, monitoring, automation, orchestration, and emerging AI-supported operational approaches in the R&E networking community. The work includes both the continued evolution of established environments and the introduction of new capabilities addressing current technical and operational needs. It covers experimental infrastructures for testing and validation, reusable workflows for network service lifecycle management, source-of-truth support for resource and service inventories, multi-tenant platforms enabling a range of operational and pilot use cases, and initial work exploring how artificial intelligence can support workflow development, operational decision support, and interaction with network management systems. One of the strengths of this work is that the individual components (Maat, orchestration workflows, GP4L and nmaas) start to form a more coherent operational ecosystem. Together, these activities provide a practical foundation that can support innovation and help NRENs assess, adapt, and adopt new tools and approaches in their own environments.

3.1 Global Platform for Labs – GP4L

The Global Platform for Labs (GP4L) provides a geographically distributed testbed for experimentation with programmable networking technologies in the research and education community. It enables users to reserve the whole or selected parts of the infrastructure in order to test networking functionalities, validate software solutions such as RARE, explore custom implementations of routing operating systems and protocols, and develop and execute their own P4 code on programmable hardware.

Figure 3.1: Snapshot of the global GP4L testbed (real-time view available on GP4L docs website [25]).

The GP4L testbed is composed of two distinct parts: GÉANT core devices and partner devices. The GÉANT core devices are managed by WP6T2 team and provide access to programmable network facilities, high-capacity switching resources, and international connectivity. In parallel, partner institutions contribute and host their own devices, which are interconnected within the wider GP4L testbed but are not managed by GÉANT. This

model extends the geographical reach of the platform and enables more distributed experiments across a wider range of hardware and deployment environments.

Within GN5-2, GP4L continues to serve as an important platform for validation, integration, and community-facing experimentation. It supports work on programmable networking and provides an environment for testing orchestrated service provisioning, AI-assisted orchestration workflows, and other reusable solutions developed within WP6.

GP4L also supported several dissemination and demonstration activities during the reporting period, reflecting its role as a practical platform for advanced experimentation. The testbed was presented on the panel on integrated infrastructure [26] at the INDIS workshop held in conjunction with SC25 in November 2025 in USA, featured in the infoshare Global Platform for Labs (GP4L) [27] in an online session in February 2025, and was presented as a security testbed at the workshop Advances in AI for Cybersecurity at ICT Innovations 2025 in October 2025 in North Macedonia [28]. It also supported Network Research Exhibition activities at SC25, including the demonstration Real-Time In-Network Machine Learning and P4 Testbed Deployment on FPGA SmartNICs, DPUs, and Switches [29], which highlighted the use of programmable infrastructure for distributed experimentation across heterogeneous targets, as well as A Case Study for Data-Intensive Traffic from Vera Rubin Observatory Supported by Path Aware PolKA Network [30], which illustrated the use of programmable networking approaches in support of demanding data-intensive science workflows.

The platform is also supported by continuously updated public documentation at the GP4L documentation site [31], where the Labs section provides detailed descriptions, open repositories, user guides, and reuse guidance for use cases developed on top of the testbed, helping the community to test, adapt, and build on these results.

3.2 Network Service Orchestration

Alongside maintaining the GP4L infrastructure, the project team addresses the automation of service lifecycle management through reusable workflows, source-of-truth-driven resource and service information, and selected AI-supported approaches, as depicted in Figure 3.2. The solutions developed in this area are intended to support more efficient and consistent network operations, while also providing practical foundations that can be reused and extended by the NREN community.

Figure 3.2: Network service orchestration architecture with an optional AI-assisted layer

3.2.1 Automated Workflows

The implementation of automated workflows for managing the lifecycle of network services is an important milestone in building autonomous and intelligent computer networks. The project team has developed workflows for L2 circuit, EVPN (Ethernet VPN) and network device interface configuration. These workflows are deployed in the PIONIER network of PCSS and they have additionally been tested as pilot deployments in the GP4L infrastructure.

The services are realised following the Infrastructure as Code (IaC) [32] approach and are based on well-established, open-source tools, including Apache Airflow (orchestrator) [33]; the Source of Truth component, Maat [34]; GÉANT LSO (for remote execution of Ansible playbooks); Ansible [35]; and Keycloak (AuthN & AuthZ) [36]. The developed network service workflows are released under an open licence [37] and can be adopted by the NREN community either in their entirety or used as a reference for creating new workflows addressing specific requirements.

The results of the work were presented at the JITEL 2025 conference in November 2025 in Spain [38], the "Global Platform for Labs (GP4L)" information meeting in February 2025 [39], the "Network Platforms Workshop" infoshare in April 2025 [40], the "Orchestration solutions for network development – WP6 update" infoshare in October 2025 [41], and in the GÉANT Connect magazine: "The Global Platform for Labs: towards reusable orchestrated service provisioning in an experimental network infrastructure" [42].

3.2.2 Maat - Source of Truth

For network operators, reliable service delivery depends on having an authoritative view of network resources, services, topology, and dependencies. Maat provides this view by acting as a Source of Truth for network resources and services, replacing fragmented documentation with a machine-readable reference point for operators, support teams, monitoring systems, and orchestration workflows.

Maat implements this role through two REST APIs, one for resources and one for services, based on a flexible data model aligned with the TM Forum [43]. This enables operators to describe both physical and logical infrastructure, as well as the services that depend on it, in a structured and extensible way. Access to Maat is managed through OAuth 2.0 and Keycloak, which provide authentication and authorisation mechanisms for controlling user and application access to the stored data.

A key advantage of Maat is that it is designed to be integrated into broader operational environments rather than used as an isolated database. One important mechanism supporting this integration is event notification. When relevant changes occur in Maat, external systems can be notified and can react to these changes. This allows Maat to become the starting point for updates in other tools and processes, such as topology visualisation, monitoring correlation, helpdesk support, or orchestration workflows.

Several integration scenarios have been tested to demonstrate this operational value. In one scenario, Maat event notifications were consumed by Grafana [44] in order to visualise stored network topology information and correlate it with monitoring data. This supports network troubleshooting by allowing operators to interpret monitoring information in the context of the known network topology and service relationships.

Another tested scenario explored how Maat information can support helpdesk and operational support workflows through a chat-based interface. Mattermost [45] was used to demonstrate how Maat can expose authoritative network information through the tools already used by operational teams. With this integration, the team showcased how Maat can support chatbot-like access to Source of Truth data and reduce the need for operators to manually search through interfaces or documentation.

Within an orchestration framework, workflows can read from Maat to determine what exists, what needs to be provisioned, and how a requested change should be applied. After the workflow executes a change, Maat can also be updated to preserve consistency between the intended state, the implemented state, and the information used by other systems. In essence, Maat is the main point from which changes can be initiated, validated, and propagated across the operational environment.

Demonstrating the transition from experimentation towards operational adoption, Maat has already been tested in several real and pilot environments. It has been used in the production environment of the Polish national network PIONIER, as well as in pilot activities within GP4L and ASNET-AM in Armenia. More recently, RENATER has started using Maat to manage the information regarding its Kubernetes clusters in the support system used for its new production perfSONAR service. These examples show that Maat is applicable beyond a single testbed, with cross-NREN reuse potential in different operational contexts.

The richer the information stored in Maat becomes, the more important it is to provide operators with intuitive ways to query complex service and resource relationships. Although the Maat user interface supports browsing and searching, traditional UI-based access becomes less efficient when operators need to query large datasets or complex relationships. For this reason, recent work has explored the use of large language models to support advanced searching and filtering of Maat data through natural-language queries. An MCP server [46] and an AI Assistant have been implemented for this purpose. This work demonstrates how Maat can be made more accessible to operators by allowing them to ask questions in natural language while still relying on structured, authoritative Source of Truth data.

The results of the work on Maat, including integrations and user stories, were presented at FOSDEM 2025 in February 2025 in The Netherlands [47], the infoshare “Network Platforms Workshop” in April 2025 [48], the 23rd SIG-NOC in October 2025 in Spain [49], the infoshare “Orchestration solutions for network development - WP6 update” in October 2025 [50], and in a dedicated article in the GÉANT Connect magazine, “Modelling the Evolving Network: Data Mastery via Flexible Schemas” [51].

3.2.3 AI-supported network orchestration

As part of the work on advanced network automation and orchestration, AI was explored in two complementary roles: as support for the development of orchestration workflows, and as an active component in controlled orchestration scenarios. The work combined desk research with practical experimentation and focused on how AI can contribute to network orchestration in ways that are useful, reusable, and relevant to NREN environments.

Vibe Coding

One line of work focused on the use of Generative AI, in particular Large Language Models (LLMs), to accelerate the design and implementation of network orchestration workflows. In this approach, the engineer describes the service intent and technical context in natural language, while the AI system assists in producing an initial workflow structure and code scaffold. Within the project, this was used to examine how AI can shorten the path from a high-level service idea to an executable orchestration workflow.

The adopted method followed two phases. First, holistic prompting was used to derive the overall workflow structure from a broad description of the service objective, technical environment, and operational constraints. This was followed by granular prompting, through which the result was refined iteratively around individual tasks, API calls, data transformations, error messages, and implementation details.

The experiments were carried out in a representative digital twin of the GP4L environment [52], using Maat [53] as the single source of truth, Apache Airflow [54] as the orchestration engine, and a ContainerLab-based GP4L topology for testing [55]. The AI assistant was provided with structured context on the service to be implemented, the orchestration environment, the available components, and the standards that had to be

respected. The workflow generation process included the production of Apache Airflow Direct Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) scaffolds, interaction with Maat for validation and retrieval of service and resource data, and preparation of configuration actions through GÉANT LSO and Ansible [56], while keeping the overall solution TM Forum-compliant. Several assistants were compared, after which ChatGPT-4o was selected for the main tests because it produced the most coherent workflow scaffolds and adapted best to iterative prompting. An important, practical finding was that starting from a clean description of the orchestration problem worked better than asking the AI to extend or reinterpret existing workflow source code.

This work showed that AI can significantly reduce the effort needed to move from concept to an initial executable prototype, particularly where the target environment is described through structured artefacts such as standards-based models, API specifications, and explicit design rules. At the same time, the experiments confirmed that AI-generated workflow logic requires human oversight to ensure that the resulting orchestration behaviour remains aligned with the intended service design and operational constraints.

The relevance of this work for the wider NREN community lies in its potential to lower the barrier to orchestration development while keeping the resulting solutions grounded in modular and standards-based building blocks. The practical results and lessons learned from this activity were shared with the network community through several channels. This approach was presented in “Modular, Standards-Based Network Orchestration with AI-Accelerated Development” at BalticNOG 2025 in September 2025, in Lithuania [57], in AI support for network workflow design and implementation at the infoshare Orchestration solutions for network development – WP6 update in October 2025 [58], and in the article “From Prompt to Provisioning: AI as Your New Network Orchestration Assistant” published in the online edition of GÉANT CONNECT magazine [59]. The presentation “From prompt to provisioning” shared at infoshare AI in Network Operations in January 2026 [60] further highlighted the practical lessons learned from using AI as an assistant in workflow design and implementation. The methodology, examples, and demonstrations of this work have also been documented in detail on the GP4L Labs [61] webpage, including supporting demo videos, providing a practical starting point for engineers and teams interested in adopting similar approaches.

AI agents for network orchestration

In parallel with the workflow-generation experiments, the team also investigated the use of AI agents in network orchestration scenarios. Here, the focus shifted from AI as a coding assistant towards AI as a reasoning and interaction layer embedded within the orchestration process itself. The explored implementations used AI agents to interpret operator requests, interact with the source of truth, reason over the required action sequence, and support human-reviewed execution of configuration changes. The main question addressed in this work was how far and in what capacity AI can participate in orchestration workflows for operational decision support, particularly in network configuration management.

This work was implemented through agentic workflows built in n8n [62], where AI agents acted as the conversational and reasoning component, while external tools and deterministic workflow logic carried out the operational steps. NetBox with its MCP [63] was used as the primary source of truth for infrastructure data, while the workflow incorporated API-based interactions for retrieving information, validating identifiers and parameters, preparing candidate changes, and only then moving towards execution. Both less constrained and more strongly guarded variants of this approach were explored in order to assess the conditions AI support becomes dependable enough to be useful in practice.

A major outcome of these experiments was the recognition that network orchestration requires a guarded agentic approach rather than unrestricted agent autonomy. Natural-language understanding, interpretation of user intent, and explanation of candidate actions were assigned to the agent, while deterministic code remained responsible for operations that must not vary. Guarding mechanisms such as output normalisation, schema-based validation, pre-action checks, and human approval before write operations were introduced to reduce the risk of unsafe or incorrect actions.

The experiments also highlighted a key practical limitation of current agentic approaches in operational environments: the difficulty of sustaining reliable multi-step tool interactions. Even when an AI system appears to understand the orchestration goal, dependable execution depends on correctly preserving state across dependent calls, using identifiers accurately, respecting preconditions, and validating the result after each step. This led to a strong emphasis on explicit contracts between workflow stages, controlled tool use, human-in-the-loop approval, and rollback or recovery measures when verification fails.

This work is relevant for the wider NREN community because it shows how AI agents can be introduced in a controlled and incremental manner, with clear separation between reasoning, validation, approval, and execution. It also provides practical examples of how to structure agentic orchestration processes and combine AI reasoning with deterministic controls in an operationally safe way.

This work contributed to the broader WP6 discussion on the role of generative AI in network management, presented in the GN5-2 “Intelligent Networks: The Rise of Generative AI in Network Management” white paper published on Zenodo in October 2025 [64]. The white paper provides a state-of-the-art review of generative AI in network management through the FCAPS framework and identifies both current capabilities and challenges for real-world network integration. Building on this broader analysis, the experience gained through this activity was shared with the network community in order to help others initiate similar work with a clearer understanding of both the opportunities and the constraints of agentic AI. The guarded approach and the lessons learned from experimenting with AI agents for orchestration were presented in “Guarded Agentic AI Approach for Network Automation and Orchestration” at the 6th SIG AI Meeting in March 2026 in Spain [65]. In addition, the detailed concepts, implementation choices, and demonstrations of both the vibe coding and agentic AI directions were made publicly available through the GP4L webpage under Labs [66], including accompanying agent skills and demo videos. This public documentation has been important in making the work accessible not only as a conceptual contribution, but also as a practical resource for engineers interested in experimenting with similar approaches. An article on Agentic AI workflows has also been published in the GÉANT CONNECT magazine [67], extending the sharing of these results and lessons to an additional professional audience.

3.3 nmaas

nmaas (formerly referred to as ‘NMaaS – Network Management as a Service’) is a platform that provides a multi-tenant secure cloud environment for application deployment supporting a range of use cases, including virtual NOCs and virtual laboratories.

The nmaas team maintains the central service instances for production and testing, supports users of both the managed and self-hosted deployments, maintains the platform catalogue and its associated open-source repositories, and assists users in contributing software and developing new use cases on top of the platform.

The nmaas platform continues its steady evolution through multiple major and minor releases. During the reporting period, platform development focused on improving identity provider integration, supporting multi-cluster application deployments, integrating with third-party components, and introducing a new user interface design. The v1.7.0 release introduced support for authentication via OIDC Identity Providers, enabling seamless integration with the new version of eduGAIN. The subsequent v1.8.0 release delivered a redesigned nmaas Portal interface, support for deploying application instances on remote Kubernetes clusters, and webhook triggers enabling integration with external automation systems. The milestone v1.9.0 release further strengthened these capabilities by introducing persisted webhook execution history, configurable domain-level resource limits, support for using a shared repository to store application configuration files, and the ability to deploy applications from standard container registries.

Work has also started on extending nmaas towards AI-assisted operations for both administrators and end users. An initial set of administrative actions is already supported through a dedicated MCP server being developed for

the nmaas platform. Building on this foundation, ongoing work introduces prompt-based application deployment and configuration, as well as AI-guided support for adding new applications to the nmaas catalogue, helping streamline application integration and lifecycle management tasks.

Since the beginning of the GN5-2 project, the two primary use cases based on the nmaas platform, namely vNOC and vLab, have been maintained as stable and mature solutions offered as part of the nmaas service. In addition, nmaas team started to define, document and promote new so-called application use cases that address common user issues or tasks using a subset of applications deployed on top of nmaas. Two such use cases were defined and disseminated during the reported period, namely Metrics and Active Monitoring, as described in subsequent sections.

The nmaas team actively disseminates project results, new use cases, and recently developed platform features through presentations at international technical and research conferences. In February 2025, nmaas was presented at FOSDEM 2025, highlighting the platform's architecture and capabilities. Subsequent presentations in September 2025 at BalticNOG 2025 in Lithuania [68] and in October 2025 at ICT Innovations 2025 in North Macedonia [69] focused on the implemented Virtual NOC (vNOC) and Virtual Lab (vLab) use cases, as well as emerging support for multi-cluster Kubernetes deployments. Later, in December 2025, the Metrics and additional application-orchestration use cases were presented at Internet2 TechEx 2025 in the United States [70]. In addition, a public nmaas group was created on LinkedIn [71] presenting information about the platform developments and participation at conferences, with posts published at regular intervals to increase outreach. nmaas was discussed during two Inforshares organised within the project. Finally, a GÉANT CONNECT magazine article was published on "Supporting Modern education using virtual labs with nmaas vLAB" [72].

3.3.1 vNOC

The nmaas Virtual NOC (vNOC) use case [73] simplifies network management by delivering a cloud-based, multi-tenant, and secure network management environment that provides access to a portfolio of monitoring and service management applications. It is designed for organizations that prefer not to deploy and maintain their own Network Management System (NMS) infrastructure, as well as for institutions and individuals seeking reliable network monitoring tools or wishing to share their software within a broader community. Through the web-based nmaas Portal, users can deploy tailored network monitoring application stacks on demand in isolated environments. This enables an integrated view of network and service operations while reducing the cost and complexity associated with in-house NMS integration and maintenance.

vNOC is offered as a production service on a central environment managed by the nmaas team [74]. It is actively used by over 120 users from more than 20 organisations including NRENs (e.g. HEAnet (now Asiera), SURF and PIONIER), R&E Institutions and GN5-2 project teams. This nmaas instance is providing access to 35 applications from the catalogue for eduGAIN-authenticated users.

3.3.2 vLab

The nmaas Virtual Lab (vLab) use case provides a cloud-based, multi-tenant environment that simplifies the organisation of hands-on exercises, training activities, and experimentation scenarios by enabling both lab managers and participants to deploy selected applications on demand within isolated workspaces. Lab managers can prepare and control training environments by enabling specific catalogue applications and managing user access, while participants can independently deploy and operate those applications within their assigned domains. The platform eliminates the need for manual hardware provisioning and complex software setup, supports bulk user onboarding (e.g., via LMS exports or SSO), and allows scalable management of course environments with automatic resource optimisation.

Typical learning areas supported by nmaas vLab include cybersecurity (e.g., exploring software vulnerabilities using controlled containerized scenarios), data analytics (running resource-intensive processing tools and simulations on centralised infrastructure), web application development (access to ready-to-use development environments with databases and application services), and DevOps (hands-on experience with CI/CD platforms without complex installation). Together, these capabilities enable efficient delivery of practical, infrastructure-independent training environments across a wide range of technical subjects.

The nmaas team provides and maintains a managed test instance of nmaas dedicated to running small-scale courses, pilots and trials at <https://vlab.dev.nmaas.eu>. During the course of the GN5-2 project Period 1, courses were organized using this environment by National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) in the subject of network management and by the University of Split for a security course.

3.3.3 Application use cases

nmaas “application” use cases provide practical, ready-to-deploy scenarios that demonstrate how the platform addresses real user needs through curated sets of applications from the nmaas catalogue. In each case, users deploy a predefined combination of tools, for example, on an nmaas-managed instance, to solve a specific task or problem identified by the nmaas team. These use cases demonstrate practical, reusable, community-oriented solutions designed to foster service adoption while showcasing nmaas capabilities. They highlight the platform’s value in delivering efficient and scalable solutions for common operational challenges.

3.3.3.1 Metrics

The nmaas Metrics [75] is a new use case providing a ready-to-deploy analytics environment built from applications available in the nmaas catalogue, including n8n, PostgreSQL, and Metabase. Together, these components support the full lifecycle of data-driven workflows: n8n enables automated data acquisition and integration from external APIs and services, PostgreSQL provides reliable storage, and Metabase delivers interactive dashboards and visualizations for exploration and reporting.

In practice, nmaas Metrics showcase how an organization can collect and correlate operational, service or project data from multiple sources and present them in unified dashboards that support monitoring and decision-making. The modular architecture allows workflows to be extended with additional connectors to external tools and automation logic, making it suitable for tracking KPIs, monitoring platform activity, or analysing usage trends. These capabilities are actively used by the nmaas team in day-to-day operations to support data-driven management and transparency. By integrating with external systems, the team is able to:

- Monitor development activity in GitLab (source code management platform) gaining visibility into contributions, workload distribution, and potential bottlenecks.
- Track application deployments and user registrations by consuming data from the nmaas Platform API, helping understand adoption trends and service growth.
- Oversee content publishing schedules through RSS integrations, ensuring regular communication and timely updates.
- Log presentations, outreach activities, or other organizational events via custom data ingestion endpoints, keeping a clear record of dissemination efforts.

By bringing together data from multiple sources into a cohesive analytics layer, nmaas Metrics transforms scattered operational information into structured insights that support informed decision-making and continuous improvement. Leveraging catalogue-based deployments of n8n, PostgreSQL, and Metabase, the

solution provides a scalable and reproducible framework for building customisable analytics environments aligned with evolving user needs.

3.3.3.2 Remote clusters management for Active Monitoring

A newly-added capability enables nmaas to centrally manage multiple remote Kubernetes clusters. That capability was leveraged for a use-case in RENATER to develop their active network performance measurement and monitoring platform. The network monitoring platform in RENATER is based on perfSONAR [<https://www.perfsonar.net/>], the active network performance monitoring and measurement architecture and toolkit.

RENATER deployed a private instance of nmaas and integrated it with its internal automation stack to automate the rollout of perfSONAR active monitoring nodes (and other applications) across France. The platform's support for distributed clusters allows RENATER to deploy and maintain measurement nodes at the network edge while still ensuring full lifecycle control from a central nmaas instance deployed on-premises. A key enabling feature is the webhook mechanism used to trigger application post-deployment automation carried out by external components, including updates to Maat as the source of truth that stores the information about Kubernetes clusters with monitoring nodes. This ensures that every perfSONAR instance deployed through nmaas is immediately registered, tracked, and operationally aligned within RENATER's automation ecosystem.

This use case is easily applicable for any organisation that needs to deploy and operate monitoring nodes in a scalable and reproducible way, while maintaining central visibility and control over the monitoring infrastructure. With capabilities introduced in GN5-2, nmaas allows administrators to define remote Kubernetes clusters (preconfigured in advance) as target locations for application deployments via the nmaas portal. In this context, nmaas provides a flexible platform for deploying active monitoring components on demand, managing them across multiple sites, and integrating them with existing operational workflows.

This use case is particularly relevant in environments where monitoring nodes need to be deployed at the network edge or across geographically distributed locations. By using nmaas, organisations can automate the provisioning of monitoring instances, manage their lifecycle through a common platform, and integrate deployment actions with external systems for inventory, orchestration, or post-deployment configuration. This reduces the effort needed to roll out and maintain active monitoring services and supports more consistent operation across distributed infrastructures.

3.4 Incubator: LogsLLM – Automated Log Analysis Using Large Language Models

The LogsLLM incubator project has developed and validated an LLM-based log-intelligence layer that addresses the growing challenge posed by the volume and heterogeneity of log data generated by network monitoring and management tools. Having NREN operational environment in its focus and leveraging the infrastructure of the nmaas service, the approach was validated using nmaas logs from Icinga, NetBox, Uptime Kuma, and firewall platforms.

The system is built on a two-agent architecture. A Standardisation Agent ingests raw logs from heterogeneous sources and normalises them into a unified JSON schema, extracting fields such as timestamp, event type, severity, hostname and source IP. An Analysis Agent then consumes this structured data to detect anomalies, correlate events across systems, and produce concise, operator-ready summaries and incident reports. Both agents operate entirely through engineered prompt templates, without model retraining — making the system model-agnostic, auditable, and easy to extend to new log sources. Analytical capabilities are exposed via a RESTful API (FastAPI [76]), supporting on-demand analysis, batch digest, historical backfill, and conversational natural-language queries.

The system was validated on-premises hosting within the PaaS/OKD cluster provided by PCSS using vLLM for strict data governance, and cloud-based deployment on Amazon Web Services via Amazon Bedrock for elastic scaling. All log data and LLM outputs are persisted in PostgreSQL, enabling structured querying, traceability, and integration with external dashboards and ticketing systems. The source code is publicly available at <https://github.com/netmode/LogsLLM>. The system was evaluated across four realistic operational scenarios — security monitoring, cross-system correlation and root-cause exploration, configuration and asset insights (NetBox), and on-demand incident review — using three LLMs: ChatGPT 4.1 mini, Llama 3.1 8B, and DeepSeek R1 14B. ChatGPT 4.1 mini achieved the highest factual accuracy and output stability across all scenarios; Llama 3.1 8B performed strongly in entity correlation. Results confirm that structured prompting combined with schema-aligned normalisation yields consistent, trustworthy summaries suitable for NOC workflows, shortening incident triage cycles and reducing alert fatigue without replacing existing monitoring platforms.

The work results were presented at the 16th SIG-NGN meeting in October 2025 in Germany [77], the infoshare “AI in Network Operations” in January 2026 [78] and in the final incubator project report [79].

3.5 Incubator: WFO RAG agent and LLM integration

The WFO RAG Agent and LLM Integration is an incubator project carried out by SURF, with the objective to design and implement a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) agent embedded directly into the Workflow Orchestrator (WFO) software, enabling users to interact with the orchestration engine through natural language queries. The project gives NREN operators full, user-configurable control over the LLM powering the search and agent functionality, supporting both self-hosted and cloud-based deployments.

The solution combines three core components: an LLM engine for natural language understanding and response generation, a retrieval mechanism backed by a PostgreSQL vector store enabling semantic, similarity-based, and structured hybrid search, and an integration layer connecting the language model with the orchestrator’s data. Indexing of the orchestrator database was implemented to allow meaningful semantic queries over subscriptions, processes, and customer data. The AI agent was built using PydanticAI [80], providing type-safe interaction between the LLM and a set of extensible tools. To enable seamless integration into modern web frontends, the AG-UI protocol was implemented via CopilotKit [81], allowing the TypeScript-based UI to parse and render Server-Sent Events (SSE) streamed by the agent in real time. The system is fully LLM-agnostic, supporting any OpenAI API-compatible model — whether open-source or proprietary, on-premises or cloud-hosted.

All defined use cases were successfully delivered: improved search accuracy over the existing implementation, a functional RAG agent capable of answering complex aggregation queries (e.g. subscription counts per customer, active process statistics, data exports), and a fully integrated UI component. The search module was contributed to the orchestrator-core open-source repository, and a UI library integration was published in the orchestrator-ui-library repository. Benchmarking across different embedding model sizes was implemented as an integration test suite to ensure reliability.

The project demonstrated that a RAG-based approach can meaningfully enhance the usability of network orchestration platforms by enabling natural language interaction, richer data analysis, and AI-assisted reporting — without requiring model training. NRENs can immediately deploy the solution by connecting any OpenAI-compatible LLM to their existing orchestrator installation.

The work results were presented at the infoshare “Workflow Orchestrator (WFO) update” in February 2026 [82] and in the final incubator project report [83].

3.6 Incubator: Workflow Orchestrator A2A Protocol Integration

In February 2026, a new incubator project started: Workflow Orchestrator Agent to Agent (A2A) Protocol Integration. Work has started on evolving the existing RAG agent into a modular, multi-agent system capable of interacting through the Agent-to-Agent (A2A) protocol, for such a multi-agent architecture to allow autonomous components to collaborate and exchange capabilities. The end of this incubator project is scheduled for the end of 2026.

4 Conclusions

This document has presented the work carried out in WP6 Tasks 1 and 2 in the areas of network technologies and platforms relevant to the R&E community. The reported activities show continued progress in the assessment of emerging technological directions, the development and maturation of practical platforms and solutions, and the sharing of results with the NREN community through experimentation, validation, documentation, training, and dissemination.

A clear outcome of the work described in this period is that WP6 continues to contribute both to forward-looking technology exploration and to the practical foundations needed for adoption and operational use. In the area of network technologies, the work has addressed topics of clear strategic relevance, including quantum technologies, network programmability, fibre sensing, and long-haul White Rabbit time distribution. Across these areas, focus has not been limited to technical investigation alone, but has also included interoperability, deployment considerations, operational aspects, training, and the identification of concrete use cases relevant to NREN environments. In this way the task helps move the discussion from general technological promise towards a more realistic understanding of how these developments may support future infrastructures and services.

At the same time, the platform-oriented work has continued to produce concrete and reusable assets for the community. GP4L has further supported distributed experimentation with programmable networking technologies and related use cases. Network service orchestration activities have advanced reusable automated workflows, strengthened source-of-truth-driven service management through Maat, and explored the role of AI both in workflow development and in controlled orchestration scenarios. The nmaas platform has continued to evolve as a multi-tenant environment, supporting production and pilot use cases in areas such as virtual network operations, virtual laboratories, metrics, and active monitoring.

In summary, quantum, fibre sensing, network programmability, time distribution, GP4L and AI use for network management and operations are at the exploratory and path-setting stage, while nmaas, Maat are production-level solutions available for immediate use. These developments show that the work goes beyond exploring new concepts to providing environments, tools, and implementation experience that can support practical reuse across different organisational contexts.

Many of the presented results are accompanied by white papers, workshops, infoshares, conference presentations, articles, public documentation, training materials, and reusable software or workflow components. This provides broader value as the outputs support knowledge transfer, comparison of approaches, and further uptake by NRENs with different levels of maturity and different operational priorities. The incubator activities described in this document further reinforce this point by showing the value of a flexible mechanism for investigating focused topics of emerging interest.

Glossary

Acronym	Definition
A2A	Agent-to-Agent
API	Application Programming Interface
C-TFN	Core Time and Frequency Network
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DWDM	Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing
EDFA	Erbium-Doped Fibre Amplifier
EVPN	Ethernet Virtual Private Network
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GP4L	Global Platform for Labs
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
KMS	Key Management System
LLM	Large Language Model
LSO	Lightweight Service Orchestrator
MCP	Model Context Protocol
NMS	Network Management System
NREN	National Research and Education Network
nmaas	Network Management as a Service
OCI	Open Container Initiative
ODA	Open Digital Architecture
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OSC	Optical Supervisory Channel
P4	A programming language for defining packet processing in programmable network devices
PQC	Post-Quantum Cryptography
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
R&E	Research and Education
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RARE	Router for Academia, Research and Education
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SoT	Source of Truth
SSE	Server Sent Events
SyncE	Synchronous Ethernet
TM Forum	TeleManagement Forum
UI`	User Interface
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
vLab	Virtual Lab
vLLM	Virtual Large Language Model serving framework
vNOC	Virtual Network Operations Centre
WFO	Workflow Orchestrator
WR	White Rabbit

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